

Poetically rich experiences: The interplay between affect and cognition

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Abstract Poetry is one of the oldest forms of art used to facilitate emotional experiences through imagery. In poetic form, ordinary experiences become intriguing, engaging and mentally challenging. With its many positive effects, poetry has much to offer to experience designers. Experience-driven design is a field that steadily seeks innovative ways to enrich product experiences. The current paper is lead by the proposition that understanding the intricate nature of everyday poetic experiences will inspire design for rich experiences. Borrowing perspectives from the fields of art, philosophy, psychology, and experience design, it introduces a new notion of 'poetically rich product experiences' and concludes that poetic richness emerges from unusually high and concurrent stimulation during cognitive and affective processes underlying product experiences. Understanding poetic richness will provide designers deeper insights into the expressive nature of products. Consequently, products can assume a unique poetic function that triggers users to bodily respond and intellectually reflect on daily phenomena abstracted into poetic experiences.

Keywords Poetry, Rich product experience, Ambiguity, Cognition, Affect, Experience design

Introduction

Poetry emerges from everyday events common to all humans and is a unique medium for artistic expression. Sources for poetic experiences are often sought in natural events as exemplified in Figure 1. Although recreating poetic experiences through objects is generally considered an intrinsic goal of art (Hunter, 2002; Williams & Harvey, 2001), poetry has found a rightful place in interaction and experience-driven design (Santokhi, 2014; Ling, Chang, & Liang, 2011; Liang, 2013; Faroughi & Faraoghi, 2013; Marti, 2015). Designers' interest in poetry comes from the noticeable effect of observed poetry on people rather than poetry as literary art. By evoking rich affective responses in people and simultaneously challenging their intellectual capacities, poetry moves people, leaves them in a state of awe, wonder, fascination and/or inspiration. The everyday moments that have such strong positive and lasting effect on people are therefore called *poetic*.

Neither designing for positive effect nor designing for rich experiences is new in the field of experience-driven design (see research concerning mixed emotions by Desmet & Fokkinga, 2012, metaphoric meaning by Cila, 2013, or pleasurable sensory experiences by Blijlevens, 2011; Hekkert, 2006; Özcan & Schifferstein, 2014). However, existing studies and good examples of design for rich product experiences have not yet considered 'richness' in its extreme state and its positively overwhelming effects on users. Analysing the poetic snow moment with the traditional terminology of experience-driven design research (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007; Hekkert & Schifferstein, 2008; Desmet & Stappers, 2011) leaves us

with the following preliminary definition for *poetic*: Anything *poetic* induces concurrently active and extremely competitive affective and cognitive processes pertaining to *aesthetic appreciation*, *discovery of new meanings*, and *implicit emotional connotations*. Thus, existing knowledge regarding rich product experiences is unrepresentative for poetically rich experiences because so far richness has been investigated through the lens of one unit of product experience (e.g., aesthetics only) rather than holistically (i.e., aesthetics, meaning and emotion all together as an experience). Through literature review in the fields of art, philosophy, psychology, and experience-driven design and analyzing existing objects that are designed to evoke (poetically) rich experiences, this paper presents first reflections on poetic richness as an experience to design.

Need for something poetic?

Our daily lives offer us a range of ordinary-to-exciting moments facilitated by designed objects (i.e., products). While some events such as making a cup of coffee or cycling to work can feel ordinary because they are part of the routine therefore nothing is notably unusual; other moments such as driving fast in an electric Tesla or discovering a new way of cooking with Le Creuset pans can feel exciting or even adventurous. It is very rare for people to experience poetic moments, similar to the snow example in Figure 1, especially induced by designed objects. Objects are traditionally designed to respond to basic human needs, i.e., physiological and safety needs as proposed by Maslow (1954). With the developments observed in the history of design and technology, utilitarian products have become mundane and expected in users'

Figure 1. Imagine a poetic moment. You are about to step into fresh snow; everything around you is crisp white and deep blue; the blue and the white are connected by branches of frozen trees; the sun is shining and reflecting on frozen but soft land; you craved to be part of that perfect untouched scene, now you are there and realize that your desire to become a part of the scene will make the perfection imperfect and that the imagined is better off as imagined than as experienced; while your imagination made the beauty your existence will defy it. What do you do? Time stands still. You contemplate to take the first step; you desire to prolong the white beauty by immersion, because destruction stays behind and the beauty waits ahead. And you discover: without experience there is no imagination. You step into fresh snow leaving a trace, not only in the snow but also in your memory, not only in the past but also in the future. (Author's imagination).

daily lives. The next big step in design history was to include users' affective responses to the designed objects (e.g., Holbrook & Hirschman, 1982; Mitchell, 1995) and make the design process more user-centered. The following trends were design for emotion, pleasure, interaction and experience (Overbeeke & Hekkert, 1999; Desmet, 2002; Norman, 2004; Hekkert, 2006). Nowadays, the technically perfected products are expected to be at least pleasurable and preferably offer a certain experience (see Figure 2) as was proposed by Pine and Gilmore (1998) as 'the experience economy'. In this vein, design for meaning has become another important ingredient to consider when designing product experiences (Govers & Mugge, 2003; van Rompay, 2008; Cila, 2014). Objects designed for experience not only indulge human senses and intellect instantly but also fulfill higher-order human needs such as 'autonomy, popularity, and stimulation (Hassenzahl et al., 2010; Özcan & Sonneveld, 2009; Özcan, 2014). Thus, the richer the experience is the more impact it will have on people's striving for a better live and a better version of themselves.

Poetry, in the sense of verse, is one of the oldest forms of art used to facilitate emotional experiences through imagery. Poetry enhances subjective-wellbeing (Hunter, 2002; Kreitler & Kreitler, 1972) by transcending moments, moving people, and transporting them into fictional worlds (Rosenthal, 1974; Selincourt, 1976). Furthermore, poetically rich moments induce creativity, facilitate learning, improve critical thinking, develop empathy and insight, and interrupt people's ordinary routine by offering them novelty, discovery, and untargeted emotions (Parr & Campbell, 2006; Routman, 2000). In poetic form, ordinary objects can become intriguing, engaging and intellectually challenging; or novel objects can feel fascinating and inspiring and invite people for interaction and explorations. Therefore poetry offers people richer experiences and longer-lasting effects.

Poetry and experience design

Poetics does not have a long history in the field of interaction and experience-driven design and only a couple of studies systematically investigated the role of poetry in design. The effect of poetry has been considered with practical demonstrations of how poetry can inspire design by providing means for narrative expressions (Desmet & Nauta, 2006; Marti, 2015) and by comparison of the creative procedures of poetry and design (Beatty & Ball, 2011). Santokhi (2014) investigated the phenomenology of naturally occurring everyday poetic experiences in order to provide designers with a set of principles to be considered when designing for poetic effect. These principles are the following: vastness (size and number of the stimulus) inspires awe, defamiliarization (looking at familiar objects from an alien perspective) leads to dissociation and estrangement, déjà vu (feelings of slight familiarity in an incongruous context) leads to confusion, ambiguity (multiple interpretation caused by perception) causes intrigue, and metaphorical representation brings new perspective. Furthermore, all these internal events have the capacity to evoke visceral emotions noticeably felt in the body.

Liang and colleagues (Ling, Chang, & Liang, 2011; Liang, 2013) have focused on the quality of interactions occurring between people and interactive objects and spaces. Ling, Chang, and Liang (2011) suggested poetic devices for interaction design such as importance of context, ambiguity (hidden object expressions), and elusive object properties (intangible materials) that would help trigger the process of imagination. Liang (2013) later suggested that poetic quality of interactions is constructed through imagination based on blocking people's ability to reason.

The doctoral study of Ionascu (2010) argued the place of poetics in design practice and suggested that poetic objects are "experimental artefacts that investigate the

Figure 2. Sony 'be moved' campaign states that Sony measures success with 'the flutter of a heartbeat and a bead of cold sweat' and that it is about what they make people feel not what they make.

everyday life of contemporary culture" and that it is the users that assign the function of such objects during experimentation and discovery. Similarly, Dunne and Rabby (2013) consider design as debate and designed objects as vehicles to carry ideology and initiate speculations about current issues in the world or future scenarios in utopias. Ionascu's as well as Dunne & Raby's stance is also relevant for the discussion on the thin line between art and design. As Munari (1966), a designer and an artist, argued that art should not be exclusive to galleries and museums but should be part of everyday life and that designers are equipped to create the same gratifying effect as art objects do (i.e., art experiences).

Although these studies introduced the need for 'poetry in design' and emphasized the added value of poetic approach on the richness of the product experience, they also pinpointed a lack of principled theory regarding poetry in experience design. Therefore, theory and practice-based knowledge is necessary concerning the quality of richness, strong psychological effects and relevance for behaviour/attitude change evoked by poetic product experiences. The ultimate goal is to enhance well-being; more specifically, to brighten people's day by offering them a sudden rush of positive feelings and thoughts within the familiarity and comfort of their everyday environment.

Rich experiences: From ordinary to poetic

Users' experiences involving designed objects can be discerned into three groups: *erfahrung* (cumulative knowledge), *erlebung* (momentary affect), and *erlebnis* (meaningful event) (Desmet & Stappers 2011; Hekkert & Schifferstein, 2008; Hassenzahl et al. 2004).

Erfahrung stems from experiences based on established practices and familiarity. If one has once driven a car, then that person has experience in driving; the more people drive the more experience they gain. Design for usability, ergonomics and co-design are concerned with such practical experiences. *Erlebung* is the experienced affect, a response, caused by an external stimulus in a certain situation. Driving an electric car may be experienced as 'exciting and joyful' or 'boring and superfluous' depending on the mindset of the driver and their context. Such product experiences have been researched and designed the most frequently in the

context of experience-driven design (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007). These experiences are further explained with three types of affective and cognitive responses: aesthetic appreciation, attribution of meaning, and emotional responses. *Erlebnis* is a holistic experience, an event, which can be narrated as a story. Driving the U.S. Route 66 in a Mustang to discover the American psyche can be a 'confronting' experience. The trigger of such experiences can be a salient object (e.g., a Mustang car) but the configuration of other relevant objects, people, and contexts further adds to the quality of an *erlebnis*. Highly abstract and complex concepts such as sustainability, luxury, love, thrill, and grief are more apt for such experience design.

Thus, the notion of richness in relation to experience differs for *erfahrung*, *erlebung* and *erlebnis*. For *erfahrung*, richness may be the fluency in various actions when operating a product. For *erlebung*, it may be the strength of bodily feelings and the amount of mental activity when interacting with products. For *erlebnis*, it may be the overall pleasantness experienced through the variety of noticeable small or big events. From the perspective of affect and cognition, it is expected that experiences get richer from *erfahrung* towards *erlebung* and *erlebnis*. *Erfahrung* experiences are utilitarian by nature and more involved with sensory-motor skills and less with affect and cognition. *Erlebung* experiences are affect- and meaning-laden by definition and the strength of affective responses and semantic associations can be manipulated through design. *Erlebnis* experiences offer a series of *erlebung* experiences and their richness is intensified by quantity and quality of sequentially occurring various experiences.

However, when investigating poetry of everyday events, Santokhi (2014) showed that participants described poetic experiences both with *erlebung* and *erlebnis* experiences (see Figure 3). For example, the sensation of light bath foam is poetic because the temptation to touch the foam makes the foam disappear (*erlebung*); or the mating dance of mayflies is poetic, because mayflies, upon years of preparation, create a magical scene while mating which symbolizes desire as much as sacrifice in the form of death (*erlebnis*). Both kinds of experiences pertain to richness experienced as a result of enhancing an

Figure 3. Two images exemplifying daily poetic experiences from Santokhi (2014) study. Images taken from Santokhi's Pinterest board 'poetic experiences'. www.pinterest.com

ongoing perceptual or cognitive process (i.e., deepening the *erlebung*) or altering the primary percept through a broad conceptual activity (i.e., broadening the *erlebnis*).

The dictionary definition of *richness* relates to large quantities, abundance, interest caused by variety, and pleasantly deep or strong sensory input (colour, sound, smell). This definition also suggests that richness is preferable because of its salience and associations to positive valence. A product experience is also considered rich when it has a significant positive effect on the user on an aesthetic, emotional, and meaning level. Fokkinga and Desmet's (2013) definition regards richness as noticeable positive impact on the user caused by mixed emotions (i.e., both positive and negative). Thus, richness is also achieved by the inclusion of negative affect. Cila's (2013) version tackles the multiplicity of meanings associated to one product through metaphors. Others consider richness in terms of intensity of multisensory pleasure (Blijlevens, 2011; Hekkert, 2006; Özcan & Schifferstein, 2014). Richness in interaction Poetic richness is often symptomized by the intensity of the felt effect. Certain moments in life can feel so overwhelming that people's time perception alters, their senses are highly stimulated or movements are slowed down; people feel puzzled as well as encouraged to take it all in and reflect on what just happened.

Poetry encountered in everyday lives is mainly about experiencing strong emotions as a result of a deep meaning searching process triggered by an aesthetically pleasing object. Thus, when searching for poetic richness, it is central to equally consider the contribution of affect (i.e., aesthetic appreciation and emotional response) and cognition (meaning attribution). It sounds logical to analyze ordinary experiences in this order too. That is, perception leads to sensory (dis)pleasure and cognition, which

ultimately affects the emotional state. However, in poetic experiences these sequential processes either unusually overlap or there is a continuous loop which updates previous mental states and feelings (Santokhi, 2014). In either case, poetic experiences cause concurrently occurring mental activities and bodily responses attributed to either one salient object (as in *erlebung* experience) or a series of objects (as in *erlebnis* experiences). As a result affect and cognition compete for sense making and bodily resources such as attention and capacity of action come short in creating an overwhelming feeling.

Affect, cognition and poetic experiences

Affect and cognition are always intertwined in the appreciation and comprehension of art objects (Silvia, 2005). Poetry, like other forms of abstract art, aims to express an affect-laden concept (e.g., love, success, grief, equality) through stimulation of senses, emotions and mental imagery in order for people to virtually experience the concept based on their previous experiences and knowledge (Shklovsky, 2009; Williams & Harvey, 2001). Starkey (2008) suggests that one needs to feel during an experience in order to fully understand it and reflect on it. During an episode of a particular experience people build new semantic links among objects and make new discoveries of meanings (Dervin, 1992; Kolko, 2010). If experiences are emotionally salient, then affect and meaning are associated and attributed to the objects facilitating the experience in a certain setting; these associations can also have a metaphorical nature (Lakoff & Johnson, 2008).

In poetic experiences, pleasure and intellectual challenge are closely connected; thus, experiencing poetry is a rewarding problem solving activity. Aesthetically salient and novel objects / events induce imagination and facilitate creative thinking, and therefore are preferable in everyday life. However,

there needs to be a trigger for the 'poetic' chain of reactions to take place. Aesthetic salience (either positive or negative) works as a good trigger because if perception results in high sensory (dis)pleasure then people become intrigued. For example, perceptible novelty draws attraction (Bianchi, 1998). Previous research (Silvia, 2005; Tan, 2000) has indicated *interest* as an emotion and an aesthetic response observed in psychology of art. Because, the appraisal of art objects is not grounded in satisfying basic needs but in satisfying higher-order needs such as need for mastery, learning, pleasure. In art objects, while aesthetic salience evokes interest (Cupchik and Gebotys, 1990), such interest is sustained by an intensive cognitive process which overloads the information processing capacity and delays comprehension (Ribeiro, 2013). Interest and delay in comprehension contribute to the affective tone and amount of mental imagery, strength of immersion and meaning making (Green & Brock, 2002). The feelings of 'time freezing' or 'being speechless' derive from the delay in information processing and retrieval.

So far in the paper, affect has been used as a general term to cover both aesthetic appreciation and emotional response. In terms of artful experiences, the distinction between the terms is not great. Aesthetics pertains to perceptual processes and is the gratification of senses; therefore, it is considered a disinterested pleasure when experiencing art (as suggested by Kant). Artists play with basic perceptual rules (e.g., complexity, novelty, symmetry) in order to create interest considering the people's repertoire of existing percepts (Hekkert, 2006). Emotional responses to art differ from emotional responses to ordinary (designed) objects. Scherer (2005) describes art-driven emotions as aesthetic emotions because such emotions (e.g., being moved, awed, or full of wonder, fascination, bliss) occur in the absence of goal appraisal and are produced by the appreciation of the intrinsic qualities of objects/events. This is further supported by the model of aesthetic appreciation and aesthetic judgment by Leder, Belke, Oeberts, and Augustin (2004). Leder et al.' model further suggests that preliminary identification of object as art (i.e., pre-classification) alters the emotional affective state of the of the viewer and frames their appreciation of art through continuous affective evaluation. Furthermore, aesthetic emotions, perhaps feelings, are also present in poetic experiences due to conceptual association and experiences to previous emotional episodes (Juslin, 2013).

Cognition follows perception and cognitive processes intend to recognize, categorize, and identify the percept. Cognition happens when conceptual associations start to emerge from semantic memory even in the absence of clear recognition or identification. For art objects, vagueness in identification, i.e., ambiguity, is preferable. As ambiguous percepts induce several nodes in sensory memories, possible configurations of objects and mental imagery start to emerge (Pavio, 2010). Moreover, natural links of conceptual association also start to emerge among the activated nodes. A wide range of conceptual activation and imagery is the aim

Figure 4. Ecology of ordinary product experiences.

of art objects following the common phrase 'art is thinking in images' (Shklovsky, 1990). In observations of art objects meaning attribution is replaced by meaning making (AKA sense making) processes. Therefore, the more ambiguous the object is the more mental search it needs to be made sense of. Metaphorical representation is another way of creating ambiguity because of the multiplicity in meaning. Moreover, poetry, a literary art, uses words to entice mental imagery, visual or musical arts use sensory input. Although it would be faster to access sensory memories via images or sound, semantic activation will be more delayed; and vice versa via poetry (Özcan & van Egmond, 2007; Özcan & van Egmond, 2009). Therefore, the imagery might be more vivid and pronounced with poetry, but senses would be more active and busy with sounds and images. Eliciting experiences through designed objects will probably activate more sensory and less semantic information; consequently affective feelings and feelings of familiarity may dominate a poetically rich experience.

Framework for poetic experiences with products

The challenge for designers is to understand how to create poetry with objects using their own set of knowledge, rules, and tools. Designers' basic knowledge pertaining to experience design (i.e., aesthetic appreciation, meaning attribution, and emotional response) mainly derives from research into psychological foundations of art (Cupchik & Gebotys, 1990; Dewey, 1934). Thus, in broader terms the interplay between affect and cognition are again central to creating poetically rich experiences. However, in a poetic experience that is by definition rich, designers would be aiming at eliciting an extraordinary activity between affective and cognitive processes that are all together gratifying. As a result, poetry experienced with designed objects would have the same function of observing art (e.g., poetry, music). That is, to momentarily transport people into an alternative world enhanced by pleasure, imagination, and feelings as a result of interactions with a limited set of physical input.

Figure 4 presents the elements that constitute the ecology of product experience by emphasizing on the inherent relationship of *product* and *user*. For an ordinary experience to happen users need to *interact* with products. These interactions can be on the level

Figure 5. Ecology of poetically rich product experiences.

of product features, product function, and product context. Physical interactions (e.g., seeing, hearing, touching) trigger multi-sensory processes and conceptual activation. Through such information processing users aim to *identify* the product (meaning), its characteristics, and its purpose, which in return *affects* the user (aesthetically / emotionally). The interactions that take place facilitate *product experiences* on *aesthetic, meaning, and emotional level*. Context influences the outcome of the experience as much as *users' and products' inherent characteristics*. The ecology of product experience resembles the user experience model of Thüring and Mahlke (2007) in a way that product and its context are considered as input for mental (affective and cognitive) processes which lead to user response. In line with this, McCarthy and Wright (2004) consider user experience as sense making process taking on five consecutive stages: anticipating, connecting, interpreting, reflecting, appropriating, and recounting. Thus, product experience is actually a holistic and complex mental process and many different components or elements need to be considered in order to understand the output as experience.

Figure 5 presents a similar ecology for poetic experiences. However, Figure 5 emphasizes on the fact that when interacting with poetically designed objects, users heavily rely on their past experiences with the world which is necessary for mental explorations and making sense of the poetic object and the elicited affect. Similarly, Law and colleagues (Law, Roto, Hassenzahl, Vermeeren, & Kort, 2009) also suggest user experience as the subset of 'everything we experience' in the world. Thus, there is a continuous loop between the current interactions and a repertoire of interactions that had already taken place; as a result, users are momentarily transported into fictional worlds laden with affect and chockfull of meaning.

Theoretically, in a poetically rich experience, all the aforementioned three product experiences

simultaneously compete with each other creating an unusually high stimulation on sensory and cognitive. Two main conclusions are the following (see Figure 6). A product experience is poetically rich when both of the following conditions are met: *i.* an object / event has an overwhelming effect on users, and *ii.* users concurrently experience a strong aesthetic response, ambiguity / multiplicity in associated meaning, and intense aesthetic emotions. Figure 6 makes use of constructs that are already familiar to the domain of experience design and research. Emotions have long been considered in design and experience of products (see, Overbeeke, Djajadiningrat, Hummels, & Wensveen, 2002), so is aesthetic experience of products (Hekkert, 2006). It has also been acknowledged that the sub-experiences of aesthetic pleasure, meaning making, and emotional response are complimentary to an overall product experience (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007). However, in current design practices and academic research regarding product experience, these sub-experiences are still designed for or studied in isolation from each other for financial, pragmatic, and contingency reasons. With poetically rich experiences (Figure 6), design practitioners / researchers are encouraged to consider and study the cumulative effect of sub-experiences of aesthetics, meaning and emotions on users and its magnitude.

Implications for poetically rich experience design

How can poetic design contribute to creation of novel experiences or enhance existing experiences? While there may be others, two options seem readily plausible considering the literature review. First, designers can choose to either enhance an ordinary object or an event and turn its qualities into poetic or create brand new objects or events that addresses issues that has never been dealt before. Secondly, designers can choose either for *erfahrung* experiences or *erlebnis* experiences with designed objects or events. In the following paragraphs these approaches will be exemplified. Furthermore, Table 1 gives an

Table 1. Design strategies for poetically rich experiences with examples.

Experience	Reason to design	Product	Example	Function*	Effect*
Erlebung	Enhance	Ordinary object	Prosthetics	Awareness	Fascinated
Erlebung	Create	Novel object	Statistical clock	Realization	Stunned
Erlebnis	Enhance	Ordinary event	Feed Love	Intensification	In wonder
Erlebnis	Create	Novel event	ReMind	Contemplation	Inspired

* The contents of Function and Effect in the table are example specific.

Figure 6. Contributors to the poetically rich product experiences. Rich product experiences individually have an effect on the user, poetically rich experiences have a cumulative effect on the user.

overview of the design strategies that may have been used in the creation of poetically rich design examples.

Design examples for poetically rich experiences

Figures 7 and 8 present four experience-driven design examples that can qualify as poetic as proposed in the paper. The examples are organized around *erfahrungs-erlebnis* experiences and novel-ordinary products and events. They are only used for demonstration of the findings of the paper and represent solely the author's opinion.

Beautiful prosthetics

Prosthetic design often feels very clinical and fails to individually represent patients who suffered from body-part amputations. Scott Summit, with 3D-printing technology, offers patients an extraordinary body part which is aesthetically compelling, and extremely desirable. The ornamented metal, glossy surfaces, shape match with the other body part add to the aesthetic appreciation of vision and touch. The new body part is more personal than the lost one because it is custom designed by taking the patient's personality and taste in aesthetic objects into account. The 'beautiful prosthetics' is an update to the older norms of prosthetic design and offers patients fascinating experiences which was unimaginable before. A negative *erfahrungs* experience caused by a standard prosthetic is now experienced as highly positive and awkwardly desirable. In the long-term Summit's design approach tackles the issue of stigmatization by shifting paradigms. It even encourages people to discuss traumatic experiences altering the focus to more constructive topics than the traumatic incident.

Statistical clock

Dunne & Raby offers a highly ambiguous object. Statistical Clock, a black wall-mounted object that vaguely resembles a lamp, mysteriously utters a number once in a while (e.g., one, three). The aesthetics of the object invites to solve the puzzle of the

mysterious of sound and shape which feel dark and gloomy. Once the users discover the meaning behind the speech, they get stunned and their percept is taken to another level. The numbers uttered in the speech represents fatalities mediated by technology (e.g., cars, trains) in an abstract way. People realize that only a technological device can announce death in the coldest way possible whereas human can relate to the importance of lives people had. As people construe the meaning of life and imagine the lives that are lost and warm feelings and sadness start to emerge. As such, a new *erlebnis* experience is created via a device that invites people to question the (im)material value of human life. Are we numbers? Are we humans?

FEED LOVE

Marije Vogelzang designs eating events (*erlebnis*). In FEED LOVE events, she enhances an eating ritual by introducing unusual objects and altering the setting. A relax setting is created for a couple of strangers, one of which feeds, the other eats, with white sheets covering not only table but also the person who is eating. This white veil, the aesthetic object, has an opening accentuated by a warm coloured circle (e.g., yellow or pink). Only the food-giver can see the food, neither party can see each other's face. The food-receiver feels protected by the veil, which facilitates a more open-minded attitude. The setting is awkward but becomes invisible when the couple starts talking about childhood memories induced by the taste of food. As the olfactory senses are intensified, the imagination goes riot and conversation gets deep; which altogether creates a very intimate and loving atmosphere. As a result, both strangers are left in wonder.

ReMind

With ReMind, a pleasurable troublemaker, Jan Brechmann materializes a highly abstract and complex concept, i.e., procrastination. ReMind is deliberately created for people to physically see the consequences of procrastinating so that they are prompted to reflect on it. ReMind is a wall-mounted large wooden ring with round tokens (pucks) and it

Figure 7. Two examples for ordinary objects and events enhanced to facilitate poetically rich experiences. Top: Beautiful prosthetics, 3D printed customized prosthetics, by Scott Summit, 2011 (https://www.ted.com/speakers/scott_summit). Bottom: FEED LOVE, an intimate platform for strangers to feed each other and converse about childhood memories, by Marije Vogelzang (<http://www.marijevogelzang.nl>).

Figure 8. Two examples for novel objects / events created to facilitate poetically rich experiences Left: Statistical Clock, facilitates reflections on technologically mediated fatalities, by Dunne & Raby, 2007 (<http://www.dunneandraby.co.uk>) Right: ReMind, facilitates reflections and actions on procrastination, by Jan Brechmann, 2013 (<http://www.pleasantroublemakers.com/#/remind/>).

turns clock-wise. The act of rotation represents time and pucks represent each personally set goal (e.g., run 6 km, call mother). The top has a barrier, when a puck makes a full rotation and reaches the top it falls. In other words, unattended events pile up and eventually create a mess by falling. This is an analogy for real-life procrastination. ReMind offers a novel ritual by connecting to people's personal lives, goals and hopes for attitude and / or behaviour change. By visualizing a mental process such as procrastination, ReMind aims to provoke reflections on one's behavioural tendencies, priorities, and time-management skills. This new ritual can be considered as an *erlebnis* experience as its impact reaches out to several different events and people.

Conclusions and future studies

This paper presented arguments for the type of richness poetic experiences may offer to users, illustrated poetic effects, suggested application domains for poetically rich experiences in the context of subjective wellbeing, and discussed consequent positive behavior / attitude change. The main argument for poetic richness was the holistic experience of sense making initiated by highly active and concurrent affective and cognitive processes. The underlying proposition is that similar to art, design can potentially help invoking poetic experiences in its own capacity by enhancing people's daily object and social interactions.

From the societal perspective, the objective is to enhance people's wellbeing with the help of poetic design. Poetry in specific and art in general has positive impacts on people (e.g., feeling refreshed, enlightened, enchanted). The function of poetic moments is to provide people with novel experiences through pleasurable intellectual challenge. By facilitating extraordinary experiences that are unfamiliar, poetic objects can offer people opportunities for amusements, realizations, and inspirations. This is an important distinction from ordinary human-product interactions. Similarly, poetic products can be designed to evoke momentary self-reflections that connect people to 'essence of life' and to underlying basic psychological processes that make people 'feel, understand, and react'. As a result, poetically rich experiences can help people to better lead their lives, enable them to see daily events differently, and act accordingly. Such attitude change is desirable, for example, for the stressful contexts of healthcare, travel, and work-life balance.

Furthermore, designing poetic experiences for ordinary objects (i.e., enhancing the experience of an existing object) may have future consequences (Sonderregger, Zbinden, Uebelbacher, Sauer, 2012) in that the aesthetic experience may wear out over time and the object may become unappealing. However, increasing the value of an ordinary object will still have more positive consequences than negative; because, the increase in the value of a daily product will also create conditions for product attachment and love (Russo, 2010).

Overall, theoretical and empirical findings pertaining to the fields of art, linguistics, human psychology, and experience-driven design yield opportunities for the application of poetic experiences and a well-studied new category of products will emerge that has the distinct goal to facilitate poetically rich daily experiences. Understanding poetic richness in such a way will provide designers deeper insights into the expressive nature of products and its power to elicit imagination and feelings. Consequently, design can assume a unique poetic function and make artful experiences more accessible to people's daily environment. Such product category will also trigger a discussion on artful experiences for the masses and whether the value of poetics will be appreciated or lost if poetry is experienced in daily environments rather than premeditated artful contexts.

The paper was heavily theoretical with some design examples in order to set the scene for poetics in design. An empirical study is being prepared to measure the hypotheses that *i.* poetically rich experiences are overwhelming and *ii.* the overwhelming feeling drives from concurrently experienced high aesthetic (dis)pleasure, ambiguity/multiplicity in meaning and strong aesthetic emotions. A set of products/events is being designed for the empirical study. The study will also compare naturally occurring poetic experiences to design induced poetic experiences in order to see the power of design in achieving extraordinary experiences.

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